

[研究文章 Research Article]

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New Records of Two Spiders, *Alcimochthes meridionalis* Tang & Li and *Irura bidenticulata* Guo, Zhang & Zhu, in Taiwan (Araneae: Thomisidae, Salticidae)

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Abstract: This study represents the first record of two spider species in Taiwan, *Alcimochthes meridionalis* Tang & Li (Thomisidae) and *Irura bidenticulata* Guo, Zhang & Zhu (Salticidae).

Key words: Crab spider, first record, identification key, jumping spider, morphological description, non-webbuilding spider

Introduction

Small non-webbuilding spiders such as jumping spiders (Salticidae) and crab spiders (Thomisidae) remain largely unexplored in terms of species diversity and distribution in Taiwan. The main reasons are their small body sizes and widespread occurrence, which make comprehensive and systematic surveys of their biodiversity difficult. Currently, no species of the genus *Irura* G. W. Peckham & E. G. Peckham (Salticidae) have been recorded, while the genus *Alcimochthes* Simon, 1886 (Thomisidae) is represented by only one species (*A. limbatus* Simon) in Taiwan.

Crab spiders (Thomisidae) are a highly diverse group of spiders, comprising 170 genera and over 2,100 species worldwide (World Spider Catalog, 2025). They are well known for their laterigrade legs and ambush predatory behavior and occupy a wide range of habitats including herbaceous layers, shrubs, and tree canopies (Pandey et al., 2024). Within Thomisidae, *Alcimochthes* is a small genus, currently containing only three known species (World Spider Catalog, 2025): *A. limbatus*, *A. melanophthalmus* Simon, and *A. meridionalis* Tang & Li. Among them, *A. melanophthalmus* lacks illustrations and has only a brief and vague external description. These three species are mainly distributed in Southeast Asia. However, their taxonomy and distribution remain poorly understood, suggesting that the genus' diversity may be underestimated.

Salticidae is the most species-rich family of spiders, currently comprising 690 genera and over 5,800 species. The genus *Irura* currently contains 23 described species, mainly distributed in Southeast Asia and southern China (World Spider Catalog, 2025). *Irura* was once considered a junior synonym of *Kinhia* (Žabka, 1985), but later studies confirmed that the genus is the senior synonym of *Kinhia* (Peng & Xie, 1994).

In this study, two spider species were recorded and described from Taiwan for the first time: *A. meridionalis* (Thomisidae) and *I. bidenticulata* Guo, Zhang & Zhu (Salticidae). Previously, both species were known only from southern China. This paper provides descriptions of their diagnostic features and a regional identification key for *Alcimochthes* in Taiwan. These two new records expand the known distributional range of these species and provide data to better understand the regional diversity of crab spiders and jumping spiders in East Asia.

Materials and methods

All specimens were deposited in the Systematics and Evolutionary Biology Laboratory, Department of Life Science, National Taiwan Normal University (NTNU). After confirming their sex, specimens were preserved in 95% ethanol and stored at -20°C . Male left palpal organs and female genitalia were dissected for examination. Female genitalia were excised using fine scissors, boiled in 10% potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution to remove surrounding soft tissues, and examined under a stereomicroscope (Olympus SZX16) equipped with a Dino-Eye digital eyepiece for imaging and measurement. ImageJ software was used for image processing, length measurements, and the addition of scale bars. All measurements are given in millimeters.

Results

Genus *Alcimochthes* Simon, 1886

Alcimochthes meridionalis Tang & Li, 2009 南方弓蟹蛛

(Fig. 1)

Material examined. TAIWAN: Taipei City: 1♀, 1 juvenile, Shilin District (士林區), 25.1362°N, 121.5350°E, 310m, V-25-2024, YUNG-KAI SHIH Leg. Aran_0001; 1♀, Shilin District (士林區), 25.1362°N, 121.5340°E, 310m, XI-22-2025, YUNG-KAI SHIH Leg. Aran_0041.

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from *A. limbatus* as follows: In *A. meridionalis*, the sides of the abdomen lack black vertical stripes, instead bearing a pale white transverse band at the base (Fig. 1A, arrows), and grayish-white tubercles of the lateral eyes (Fig. 1B, arrows) (Tang & Li, 2009). In *A. limbatus*, the abdomen shows distinct black longitudinal stripes along both lateral margins in dorsal view, and grayish-brown tubercles of the lateral eyes (Tang & Li, 2009; Rio & Matsumoto, 2020). The ducts and spermatheca are both twice as long in *A. limbatus* as in *A. meridionalis*.

Description (Aran_0001). Total length 3.8, prosoma length 1.8, opisthosoma 2.0 length. Leg measurements: I 6.3 (1.8 + 2.2 + 1.6 + 0.4 + 0.3), II 6.7 (2.0 + 2.3 + 1.7 + 0.4 + 0.3), III 3.8 (1.1 + 1.5 + 0.6 + 0.3 + 0.3), IV 4.1 (1.3 + 1.5 + 0.7 + 0.3 + 0.3). Leg formula: 2143. The ocular quadrangle is wide and trapezoidal, with the posterior lateral eyes positioned on the edges of the carapace in dorsal view. The abdomen is oval, slightly narrowed distally, with a white line on the dorsal proximal region (Figs 1A–B). Epigynum with a large, sclerotized plate; copulatory ducts short and twisted; spermathecae reniform (Figs 1C–D).

Distribution. China (Yunnan: Xishuangbanna), Taiwan (Taipei) (New record).

Figure 1. The Taiwanese specimen of *Alcimochthes meridionalis* Tang & Li, 2009. A. Body, dorsal view; B. Dorsal view of the carapace; C. Epigynum, ventral view; D. Vulva, dorsal view. Scale bar: 1 mm.

Genus *Irura* G. W. Peckham & E. G. Peckham, 1901*Irura bidenticulata* Guo, Zhang & Zhu, 2011 雙齒翹蛛

(Fig. 2)

Material examined. TAIWAN: Taipei City: 1 ♂, Shilin District (士林區), 25.1372°N, 121.5360°E, 310m, V-27-2024, YUNG-KAI SHIH Leg. Aran_0008.

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from *I. trigonapophysis* (Peng & Yin) as follows: The abdomen of *I. bidenticulata* has two brown transverse bands and a central longitudinal stripe, along with brown dotted markings; before preservation in alcohol, the entire body exhibits a purplish-red metallic sheen, and the conductor is more curved compared to that of *I. trigonapophysis* (Guo et al., 2011). In contrast, the abdomen of *I. trigonapophysis* has a white longitudinal stripe in dorsal view formed by white hairs, outlining a triangular shape; before preservation in alcohol, the body is black and lacks metallic gloss (Peng, 2020).

Description (Aran_0008). Total length 3.7, prosoma length 1.7 opisthosoma length 2.0. Leg measurements: I 4.7 (0.8 + 1.3 + 1.3 + 0.8 + 0.5), II 3.0 (1.0 + 0.6 + 0.5 + 0.5 + 0.4), III 2.5 (0.9 + 0.3 + 0.5 + 0.5 + 0.3), IV 2.9 (1.0 + 0.5 + 0.6 + 0.5 + 0.3). Leg formula: 1243. The dorsal body has a metallic sheen (Fig. 2A). Leg I is long and robust, with one ventral spine on the tibia, two ventral spines on the metatarsus (Fig. 2B, arrows). The male palpal organ has a membranous structure at the joint, the cymbial process (CP) is enclosed by the retrolateral tibial apophysis (RTA), the embolus (E) is long and thin (Figs 2C, D), and the cymbial process is bent inward (Fig. 2D).

Distribution. China (Hong Kong, Hainan), Taiwan (Taipei) (New record).

Figure 2. The Taiwanese specimen of *Irura bidenticulata* Guo, Zhang & Zhu, 2011. A. Body, dorsal view; B. Leg I of the right view, dorsal view; C. Palpal organ, ventral view; D. Palpal organ, retro-lateral view. Scale bar: 1 mm. Abbreviations: CP = cymbial process, E = embolus, RTA = retrolateral tibial apophysis, T = tegulum.

Discussion

This study provides the first records of *Alcimochthes meridionalis* and *Irura bidenticulata* in Taiwan. The specimens of *I. bidenticulata* collected from Taiwan show slight differences from the original description: The tibia of leg I bears only one robust ventral spine, whereas the specimens described in the literature have two ventral spines on both the tibia and metatarsus, and the tibia is relatively more slender and shorter (Guo et al., 2011; Logunov, 2022). However, based on body color pattern and genital characters, the specimens are identified here as this species. This finding expands their known distribution ranges and highlights that spider surveys in Taiwan remain incomplete, particularly for small-bodied, non-web building groups. Biogeographically speaking, these new records support the hypothesis of a close relationship between Taiwanese and Chinese biological systems (Zhu, 2016), reflecting the continuity of East Asian fauna and the potential historical dispersal routes between Asian mainland and the island of Taiwan.

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南方弓蟹蛛與雙齒翹蛛在臺灣之首次紀錄 (蜘蛛目：蟹蛛科、蠅虎科)

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摘要: 本研究報告南方弓蟹蛛 (蟹蛛科：弓蟹蛛屬) 與雙齒翹蛛 (蠅虎科：翹蛛屬) 在臺灣之首次紀錄。

關鍵詞: 蟹蛛、新紀錄、檢索表、翹蛛、形態描述、非結網蜘蛛